
***Thecidea papillata* (von Schlotheim 1813) from the Late Maastrichtian
'Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata'-bed (Jauche Member)**

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Brachiopoda

Class: Rhynchonellata

Order: Thecideida

Family: Thecideidae

Genus: *Thecidea*

Species: *Thecidea papillata*

Author Citation von Schlotheim 1813

GEOLOGICAL TIME SCALE

Eon: Phanerozoic

Era: Mesozoic

Period: Cretaceous

Sub Period: None

Epoch: Late

International Age: Maastrichtian

STRATIGRAPHY

The fossils are associated with a coarse-grained biocalcarenite ("Tuffeau jaunâtre à *Thecidea papillata*"-bed), part of the (Late Maastrichtian) Jauche Member (**Bless et al.** 1990).

PROVENANCE

Collector: Nick Van Liefferinge (NVL)

Date Collected: 02/15/2025

Acquired by: Field collection

LOCATION

Jauche-la-Marne
Orp-Jauche
Walloon Brabant
Belgium

REFERENCES

Bless M.J.M., Felder P.J. & Jagt J.W.M. 1990: Repeated Tethyan influences in the Early Campanian to Middle Late Maastrichtian successions of Folx-les-Caves and Orp-le-Petit (Eastern Brabant Massif, Belgium), *Annales de la Société Géologique de Belgique*, T. 113 (fascicule 2), pp. 179-197.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2